

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

3D Printed Continuous Carbon Fiber Reinforced PEEK Composites

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1. Background

Why does PEEK get so much attention?

- Poly(ether ether ketone) : PEEK
 - **Semi-crystalline** Polymer
- Advantages
 - High **thermal stability**
 - Desirable **mechanical properties**
 - **biocompatibility** and **Safety**
 - **light weight**.
- Applications
 - Field of Cars,
 - Aircraft,
 - **Bone implants** to replace metal

PEEK as biomaterials for spinal implants [1]

1. Background

Additive manufacturing (AM)

Especially for FDM tech.

- General plastics and Engineering plastics are easy to print but the performance is poor;
- Special engineering plastics are relatively high performance but hard to print.

Material types for FDM

1. Background

- Short fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites by FDM;
- Inherit the advantages of 3D printing: fabricating composites with a low cost, a simple process and complex structures;
- Limited improvement of mechanical performance, just about 30%.

2. Process for CCF/PEEK composites AM fabrication

Process of 3D printed CCF reinforced thermoplastic Composites [2]

- Excellent performance for printing CCF-PLA/ABS composites etc.
- But for CCF/PEEK composites, two main problems exist, weak interlayer bonding and low impregnation.

2. Process for CCF/PEEK composites AM fabrication

- Main method_PEEK impregnation & laser assistance [3]
- Main test_Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS)

Process of 3D printed CCF reinforced PEEK Composites [3]. a) pre-impregnation, b) fiber tow after impregnation, c) extrusion 3D printing with laser heat treatment, d) printed samples, e) standard sample for ILSS test as f).

3. Results for CCF/PEEK composites AM fabrication

Impregnation

- As the fiber pulling speed and the applied temperature increase, the degree of impregnation increases;
- 10mm/min & 410 °C
- As the viscosity of the resin decreases, the degree of impregnation increases.
- MFR, ≥ 30 g/10min

3. Results for CCF/PEEK composites AM fabrication

Interlayer bonding

Laser supplies concentrated heat source and rapidly warming up.

3. Results for CCF/PEEK composites AM fabrication

- After laser assistance
- Crystallinity, 15% to 31%;
- Less delamination;
- Failure mode changes.

3. Results for CCF/PEEK composites AM fabrication

When Fiber content over 40%.

	ILSS	Flexual Strength	Flexual Modulus	Tensile Strength
Strength	56MPa	503MPa	40GPa	394MPa

4. What to do next?

- **Future work**
- a) Regionally controllable gradient stiffness/ modulus/ crystallinity in one part as wanted?
- b) Much better bonding from microscopically to macroscopically?
- c) Equipment upgrade (based on Combot-I form Shaanxi Fibertech...)?

Reference

- [1] Toth J M, Wang M, Estes B T, Scifert J L, Seim HB 3rd, Turner AS. Polyetheretherketone as a biomaterial for spinal applications[J]. *Biomaterials*, 2006, 27(3):324.
- [2] Yang C, Tian X, Li D, Cao Y, Zhao F, Shi C. Influence of thermal processing conditions in 3D printing on the crystallinity and mechanical properties of PEEK material[J]. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 2017, 248:1-7.
- [3] Luo M, Tian X, Shang J, Zhu W, Li D, Qin Y. Impregnation and Interlayer Bonding Behaviours of 3D-Printed Continuous Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced Poly-ether-ether-ketone Composites, *Composites Part A*, 2019, S1359-835X(19)30099-5

Thanks for your attention.

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